

ART STUDIES

THE INNOVATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF TRADITIONAL CHINESE MINORITY MUSIC IN THE CONTEMPORARY CULTURAL BACKGROUND

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Abstract

The diversification of modern culture has had a profound impact on minority music culture, with opportunities and challenges coexisting. The creation and progress of Mongolian music are very evident in this, as it is closely related to its own traditional music and cultural environment, always maintaining its own ethnic characteristics; By embracing and absorbing the music culture of other ethnic groups with a broad mind, we can communicate and integrate well with other music cultures, continuously improving our own development ability; Continuously improve oneself in order to better meet the requirements of social development. Only by completing the transformation from tradition to modernization as soon as possible can Mongolian music have better development opportunities

Keywords: ethnic music, traditional Chinese culture, development, social needs, modernization.

Music is an important type of art that showcases the inner thoughts and concepts of human individuals or groups, constantly changing with the progress of social history. Nowadays, the world economy is more closely connected, there are more cultural forms, and various ethnic cultures converge and seek differences to coexist. The close economic connections, the informatization of communication, and the diversification of culture will definitely have a significant impact on traditional art in China. The progress and development of Mongolian music is facing great challenges. How to find new ways of development amidst challenges is a problem that relevant personnel need to solve. Based on the analysis of the current cultural environment, this article comprehensively explores the creation and progress of Mongolian music.

The Mongolian people have had many music resources from ancient times to the present, including a few recorded ancient music in historical materials, ancient ethnic music spread through folk literature and folk dissemination, and so on. Under the integration of modern multiculturalism, the external environment on which Mongolian indigenous music relies has undergone significant changes, with some folk songs and music lacking corresponding dissemination and singing environments. Traditional functions are also gradually fading and are slowly disappearing, and even some music has disappeared. We will use the Mongolian long tune as an analysis case. Nowadays, there have been significant changes in the production and lifestyle of Mongolian herdsmen, with Mandarin Chinese becoming the common language. The previously lush grasslands have also transformed into agricultural areas and cities, and the long tune has gradually lost its external environment for survival and development. Now, we can no longer see the presence of the long tune in areas such as the East Tümet and Horqin regions. Only in a very small number of elderly people and professional analysts can we see the charm of the long tune. Changdiao is slowly leaving the grassland.

Changdiao is a song from the Mongolian region, but now, the Mongolian people are gradually forgetting Changdiao, and grassland civilization is transforming into agricultural and industrial civilization. The actual development situation indicates that if we cannot spread, maintain, and develop long tune, we can only wait for the long tune to disappear. But if we want to protect the original ecological music, we cannot limit the development of civilization. We need to change our own development philosophy, actively communicate with the current society, and meet the development needs of modern civilization. Based on the above situation, we can use the following protection methods:

1. Maintain one's own vitality throughout its early stages of appearance. Government agencies need to motivate and support the people of pastoral areas to maintain the vitality of the original ecological music through the model of teacher apprentice inheritance.
2. Cultural institutions need to maintain and preserve the original ecological music resources through practical inspections, information collection, documentary production, recording, and archiving. The creation and progress of Mongolian music cannot be achieved at the cost of abandoning its own musical characteristics or losing ancient artistic concepts. Due to the fact that ethnicity is a crucial part of Mongolian music, it is the biggest difference between itself and other music. Therefore, under the impact of contemporary technology, economy, politics, and various cultures, how can Mongolian music maintain its unique charm and reflect contemporary characteristics? I think we need to start with the following parts:

One is the content that Mongolian music needs to spread. Whether now or in the future, what it aims to convey is always the aesthetic connection between history and the actual life of the Mongolian ethnic group. The above connection not only includes various social connections of the ethnic group, but also includes the internal spirit and concepts of the ethnic group in social relationships, ethnic feelings, and the unique perception patterns of the people towards their own lives.

The second is the way Mongolian music is conveyed and the use of technology. The Mongolian ethnic group embodies a unique way of music communication, using their own musical rhythms to create music and singing in their native language, fully demonstrating the aesthetic characteristics of their own people. In addition, selecting suitable music expression methods has also had a crucial impact on the transmission of the ethnic characteristics of Mongolian music. For example, adding new musical elements that meet the requirements of contemporary society in terms of text and music expression types, further meeting the development needs of modern society. However, we cannot excessively seek economic benefits under the guidance of current consumer culture, utilize hype and celebrity effects, modify Mongolian music through popular fashion, and make unfounded adaptations. Moreover, we cannot use curiosity to show content that does not conform to social development trends. The shallow and rough adaptations of ethnic music mentioned above are not conducive to the inheritance and development of Mongolian ethnic music.

The third is the emotions and creativity of Mongolian music creators. At present, Mongolian music creation is gradually transforming from a group to an individual, from spontaneous development to consciousness. The emotions and ideas of music creators towards their own ethnic group, as well as their understanding of the lives of the people of that ethnic group, play a very important role in the quality and value of national art. Music creators not only need to prevent abnormal ideas arising from the expansion of national pride, but also cannot abandon their own musical form and blindly seek the music of other ethnic groups. In terms of aesthetic consciousness, the mode of artistic production is the unity of artistic expression level and aesthetic relationship. In the current economic and social context, there have been significant changes in the cultural expression system. To perfectly integrate the Mongolian music genre with the complex aesthetic relationships in modern society, the essence is to combine the above three parts and comprehensively and deeply convey the living environment and development needs of modern Mongolian music. Its essence is very difficult. Whether it is the art of any ethnic group or even all cultures, it embodies a certain degree of vitality and development. This vitality and development can not only have a certain impact on the improvement of the aesthetic quality of one's own nation, but also have an impact on the shaping and changing of cultural personality and cultural concepts. To a certain extent, it will also affect other types of civilization forms. Ultimately, it becomes a key aspect of human civilization's wealth, and only in this way can culture achieve more long-term development.

After China's reform and opening up, many Mongolian music workers began to deeply explore folk music materials based on their own national emotions, and began to create unique music works that showcase social spiritual concepts and coordinate ideas with culture, accelerating the further development of Mongolian music industry. Now Tenger, Siqin Chaoketu and many other musicians continue to inherit the essence of

their own national music, absorb contemporary music culture, and create outstanding works with ideological and appreciation. Singer Tenger's main work, *Heaven*, not only incorporates his deep feelings for his hometown into his works, but also incorporates his concerns about the ecological environment of his hometown into the song. In addition, many young people's groups, such as the Wolf Band and Zero Point Band, have also incorporated new musical concepts while inheriting their own ethnic music characteristics, and have also made new attempts in the pioneering part of Mongolian music. It has laid a solid foundation for the development of Mongolian music. In the current information society, the diversity of economy and culture is more evident, and communication between different ethnic groups is necessary. Therefore, Mongolian music also needs to absorb the excellent cultures of other ethnic groups in the development process. The overall trend of the development of this ethnic music is good, but there have also been many problems in communication between ethnic groups. There are still many shortcomings in the maintenance and dissemination of Mongolian original ecological music, as well as in the self adjustment part. Therefore, in the modern cultural environment, the creation and progress of Mongolian music require special attention to the following parts:

1. In terms of philosophy, we should adhere to the basic principles of openness and tolerance, and also pay attention to diversity when seeking national identity. Every type of music in the world is evolving through change, and there is no music that remains unchanged forever. Global openness will definitely promote the integration and complementarity of various types of music. Good and reasonable music will definitely replace conservative and unreasonable music. If the relevant personnel still do not attach importance to the diverse cultures of the world, do not rely on various favorable factors, and continue to develop their own ethnic culture in isolation, then the original ecological music of the Mongolian ethnic group will definitely be severely affected. If culture no longer absorbs the music culture of other ethnic groups, it will definitely cause harm to oneself. Relevant personnel need to constantly broaden their horizons, use their own hearts to absorb other types of culture, absorb and accept the good parts of foreign music culture that meet the needs of social development when communicating with other music cultures, and achieve new development in the integration of various ethnic music culture concepts and value trends. Communication is not just about mutual acceptance, it is also a form of interaction. The ultimate result of interaction is to preserve the most distinctive part of various types of music, which is the most important part of music culture. In this section, musicians have already made their own efforts. For example, as a well-known singer, La Sorong has absorbed the advantages of vocal techniques from other ethnic groups, including foreign music, while inheriting and disseminating the characteristics of national vocal music, perfectly handling the problem of breathing and the integration of long and short notes. It occupies a place in the development history of Mongolian music and also

reflects its unique characteristics and style. Received recognition and affection from the audience.

2. The relationship between maintenance, inheritance, development, and creation is mutually influenced. Maintenance is the prerequisite for dissemination and development, development is the ultimate goal of maintenance, and innovation is the key way of development. The development of human music has shown us:

The most reasonable maintenance for ethnic music is to constantly make changes according to social development trends; The most reasonable way to spread ethnic music is to combine it with the source of development. Development is the absolute principle, and innovation is the most important driving force. With the transformation of society, the economy and culture have undergone tremendous changes, and the internal thinking and values of the public are also changing. Relevant personnel can also correctly absorb the good music content of other ethnic groups when disseminating their own national music. However, this absorption is not unfounded or unreasonable, and we need to select appropriate content for reference. Spreading music is to fully absorb the good parts of ethnic music culture, absorb the parts that conform to the laws of social development, and then spread and promote them in daily life. However, in the above process, good innovation is necessary. Innovation is the use of types and methods of recreation to enhance the sociality and realism of music. Only in this way can ethnic music become a completely new type of music content, complete the transformation from tradition to modernity, and achieve the long-term development goals of ethnic music as soon as possible. Therefore, for Mongolian music, it is very important to transform its own music correctly, enhance its artistic charm, and make it conform to contemporary aesthetic standards while emphasizing its own musical characteristics and maintaining its unchanged connotation. The singing style of famous singer Szege Ri reflects diversity; Firstly, immersed in the national ideology of the bloodline, followed by the contemporary concept of seeking self-worth. It transforms many Mongolian folk songs and uses contemporary singing methods to perform, integrating the unique style and contemporary elements of the ethnic music. This is the deep discovery and innovation of ethnic music. The new singing of folk songs gives new cultural ideas and characteristics of the times, fully showcasing the national characteristics and style of music.

3. When integrating with the art market, find more favorable development opportunities. The development of ethnic music is closely related to society, politics, and economy in reality. Therefore, the integration of ethnic music and the art market is an important way for ethnic music to progress.

For a long time, the number of tourists coming to Inner Mongolia has been continuously increasing, which is closely related to the rich geographical and cultural resources of the region, as well as the charm of ethnic music itself. The modern multicultural environment provides a wide range of options for the development of Mongolian music, with various art festivals, cultural villages, and other dissemination modes,

providing a platform for communication between Mongolian music and other types of music. In other words, for Mongolian music, it is not only a spiritual product, but also a good economic resource with development potential. In addition, the contemporary production mode of ethnic music and the combination of economy are bidirectional.

4. Use contemporary technology to continuously complete the transformation from tradition to modernization. Marx's viewpoint on artistic production points out that the mode of artistic production is closely related to the development of productivity in any period. The emergence of ethnic music in ancient society was closely related to religion, sacrificial ceremonies, and material production activities. In the social environment at that time, the independent dissemination of ethnic music emerged. However, in the contemporary industrial environment, the production mode of contemporary ethnic music in a brand new cultural environment is folk culture and the preparation of distinctive music materials by artists, allowing some personnel to organize, raise funds, create, adapt, and then utilize the unique singing skills of actors. The development of modern Mongolian music not only relies on the spontaneous participation, dissemination, and learning of its own ethnic groups, but also on the independent dissemination and innovation of the government, media, and art workers. In modern society, the impact of technology on art production, including ethnic music, is very evident. We can see the use of high-tech methods in today's ethnic concerts, square stage manufacturing, lighting and sound equipment, and celebrity accompaniment performances. As some experts have said: in modern art production, technological ideology uses technological methods and materials. However, in the above situation, some people are also beginning to worry that technological rationality will blur the characteristics of Mongolian music, ultimately leading to the shift of Mongolian music away from ethnic life and towards mass music. Indeed, contemporary technology may cause the loss of some elements in Mongolian music, but at the same time, it also brings more favorable media and service methods to the dissemination and promotion of Mongolian music, and adds vitality to the new development of Mongolian music.

5. Strengthen the cultivation of Mongolian music and cultivate talents with high comprehensive quality. Innovation and progress require the cultivation of more music talents. Talents are the key driving force for the development and progress of Mongolian music and an important foundation for promoting the development of Mongolian music. The focus of competition is the competition for talent. In the modern cultural environment, in order to find a new direction for the development of Mongolian music, it is necessary to have a large number of high-quality talents who not only understand the content of Mongolian culture but also grasp the development direction of Mongolian music. The creation and progress of Mongolian music is our ultimate goal. The achievement of this goal requires the comprehensive development of ethnic music education. The Art School of Inner Mongolia University and the Conservatory of Music of Normal University are important bases for

cultivating music and art talents in the region. They have long cultivated numerous music talents such as Dedema, Lasurong, Tengger, etc. for the teaching of ethnic music theory. In addition, there are many well-known artists who have left the stage and returned to the grasslands to raise funds to hold various types of music schools. For example, seeking trainees from herdsmen to cultivate more talents for the region. In 2001, Qi Baoli Gao led 1000 global horse head qin players to perform at the first Youth International Horse Head Qin Art Festival held in Hohhot, and received a very good response. This program was also recorded in the Guinness World Records. The style and characteristics of Mongolian music have been well reflected in the global music industry, promoting the development of contemporary Mongolian music.

In summary, the diversification of modern culture is a new challenge and a good opportunity for the development of Mongolian music culture. The innovation and progress of Mongolian music are inseparable from the traditional cultural environment of the Mongolian people. On the basis of maintaining national individuality, we use our own hearts to absorb and learn from other types of music culture, communicate with other music cultures independently, and continuously improve our own development strength; To better meet the development needs of modern music and complete the transformation from tradition to modernization.

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THE INDIVIDUALITY AND TRAITS OF CHINESE ETHNIC MUSIC

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Abstract

China is a multi-ethnic country, with 56 ethnic groups each having their own characteristics, and the history of ethnic music has a long history, with unique artistic and aesthetic characteristics. China's ethnic music presents unique features, diverse styles and diverse forms and genres, with strong inclusiveness and development. In the process of historical development, ethnic music has been able to maintain a high degree of consistency between aesthetic characteristics and artistic features, mainly because China's ethnic culture can correctly understand the connotation of ethnic music art. On this basis, this article briefly analyzes the artistic personality and characteristics of China's ethnic music, hoping to effectively promote the sustainable development and innovation of ethnic music culture, and effectively highlight the unique artistic quality of China's ethnic music.

Keywords: ethnic music, artistic personality, traits, diversity, inclusiveness.

1. Concept of Chinese Ethnic Music

Ethnic music refers to ethnic music that is unique, artistic, and humanistic in the historical development process of a certain nation or country. Ethnic music not only includes local and folk music programs and traditional works, but also includes folk music programs or music works adapted from elements, vocal works created according to folk music specifications or forms, and so on. The ethnic music mentioned in this article refers to Chinese ethnic music, which has a diverse and diverse style and a long history of development. Combining the concept of folk music, Chinese ethnic music can be divided into two parts: 1. Traditional ethnic music includes traditional opera and folk songs, quyi, dance and instrumental music, and rap music art forms. For example: Errenzhuang, Beijing Opera, Yue Opera, Pingju, etc., Taiping lyrics and Suzhou Pingtan, Beijing Rhyme Drum, etc. 2. Ethnic music works that combine traditional Chinese music repertoire and creative elements, as well as traditional music forms and specifications. Wang Luobin is known as the Western Song King Wang Luobin's music works, which have strong representativeness. Wang Luobin is particularly fond of Xinjiang music art and has created a large number of classic vocal works based on Xinjiang folk songs, such as "Raise Your Head", "In That Faraway Place", and "Youth Dance". Based on the numerous characteristics mentioned above, it indicates that Chinese ethnic music has strong aesthetic and artistic characteristics.

2. The Artistic Characteristics of Chinese Ethnic Music

(1) Inclusiveness

Chinese ethnic music has artistic characteristics and strong personality, mainly due to its developmental and glorious nature. Whether it is opera, folk songs, or

rap art, there are relatively mature music specifications and forms, but the content is not fixed. Each ethnic music art form will be created in combination with social culture and historical background, so it will be based on the diverse development needs of society, Derived new music tracks and works. For example, during the reign of Emperor Qianlong, the economy was established and gradually developed, and to this day, the repertoire of Peking Opera has gradually enriched and updated without stagnation. The economy has strong artistic specifications and expressive value, with a large number of classic songs, such as "Three Claws", "Yutang Spring", "The Gathering of Heroes", "Picking a Pulley", "Picking up Jade Bracelets", and other new songs that combine the characteristics of the times. For example, Mei Lanfang, a famous theatrical theorist during the Republic of China period, is one of the most representative works of New Beijing Opera, such as "Luoshen", "Tiannu Sanhua", and "Yizhaoma". Whether it is the new Peking Opera repertoire or the significance of its development, it not only enriches the total number of Peking Opera, but also comprehensively improves the scale and level of Peking Opera art from various aspects such as its artistic ideas and concepts, spirit and expression methods, upper forms and costumes, and stage settings. The above are sufficient evidence that China's ethnic music art has strong inclusiveness and development, constantly innovating and developing in the long river of history, and is unique.

2. Diversity

The forms and genres of ethnic music art in China have strong ethnic characteristics and styles, distinct artistic personalities, and are mainly closely related to the cultural and geographical environment. China has a